

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D.5.5

Report on the standardisation landscape and applicable standards

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Publishable Summary

The deliverable D5.5 is produced in the context of BIO-SUSHY-WP5, Task 5.4 – Standardisation activities, in particular the subtask 5.4.1 *Analysis of the applicable standardisation landscape*. This deliverable includes as its main contribution the identification and analysis of the standardisation technical committees (TCs) at European and International standardisation level related to the BIO-SUSHY project as well as the published standards and standards under development that can be relevant and useful for all the project activities in each BIO-SUSHY/WP.

The Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE), as a European Standardisation Body, is a partner in the BIO-SUSHY project to advise, manage and develop all the activities related to standardisation, supporting the use of existing standards and the generation of new ones in line with the 2021 EU Policy on Knowledge Valorisation and the 2022 EU Strategy on Standardisation. The objective is to increase the impact of the project on industry, regulators and society. In order to fulfil this commitment, this deliverable has been prepared to guide the partners about the published standards and standards under development that can be applicable and are related to the BIO-SUSHY-WP tasks.

This deliverable will also serve as the starting point for the development of the BIO-SUSHY Strategy for the contribution to standardisation in Task 5.4.2. It shows the technical committees that have developed applicable standards and will identify the most relevant ones for the dissemination and collaboration activities. It also allows us to identify gaps in current standardisation that the results of the project may fill. These two aspects will be considered in the conclusions.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AMD	Amendment to a published standard document
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC/CLC	European Committee for Standardisation in the Electrical field
COR	Correction to a published standard document
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
DIN	German Institute for Standardisation
ECMM	European Community Monitor Mission
ECCM	European society for composite materials
EN	European Standard
EU	European Union
FprEN	European Standard under development for formal vote
JWG	Joint Working Group
IRISS	Infrastructure for Resilience, Interconnectivity and Security by Satellite
ISO	International Standards Organisation
ISO	International Standard published by ISO
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEC	International Standard published by IEC
NSB	National Standardisation Body (UNE, DIN, AFNOR etc.)
PFAS	Polyfluorinated alkyl substances
prEN	European Standard under development for public enquiry
SC	Subcommittee
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable-by-Design
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardisation/Spanish national standard
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item
WP	Work package

Introduction

This deliverable contains a detailed study on the relevant Standardisation Technical Committees at the international and European levels in the scope of the BIO-SUSHY project activities as well as relevant standards developed in these committees. The objective of the standardisation activities in the project is to facilitate the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the project results. Other objectives are the provision of starting information for the project activities with regard to what already exists in the market through standard in order to provide for compatibility and interoperability as well as to use the standardisation system as a tool for the dissemination of the project results and the interaction with the market stakeholders.

This document contains the following:

- an overview of the relevant international and European standardisation system;
- a detailed list of the standards and normative documents as well as standards and normative documents under development relevant for BIO-SUSHY.

1. THE CONTEXT: BIO-SUSHY PROJECT

BIO-SUSHY aims at developing innovative coating solutions that will be designed to meet the policy ambition of the EU's chemical strategy for sustainability toward a toxic free environment. BIO-SUSHY particularly targets to develop novel bio-based durable water and oil repellent coatings (sol-gel and powder) which will be validated in 3 target markets: textile, food packaging and packaging for cosmetic applications. To achieve the objectives the development will be based on 3 pillars, R&I (Research and Innovation) coating development, supported by computational modelling of coating performances, toxicity assessment and by SSbD (Safe and Sustainable-by-Design) methodology to ensure safety and environmental performances, with a decrease by 25 % of environmental impact. Best practice methodology set through EU programs (ECMM, ECCM, IRISS...) will be followed and implemented to ensure excellence of the research and outputs which will be further optimised through a program of data harmonisation and management.

In this project, standardisation activities are employed to maximise the impact of the developed solution, and to facilitate their acceptance and utilization by the target markets. In order to provide starting information for other WPs, and ensure compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market through standards, this document contains a list of standardisation technical committees and standards relevant to the BIO-SUSHY project. This document has been developed as a result of task T5.4.1 *Analysis of the applicable standardisation landscape (M1-M6)*, corresponding to the WP5 Measures to maximize impact.

No official updates of this document are foreseen in the project plan. Nevertheless, a continuous follow-up of the activities of relevant Standardisation Technical Committees and their standardisation developments will be provided throughout the project's lifetime.

Deliverable D5.5 forms the basis for the activities of task T5.4.2 *Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments*, which extends from M7 to the end of the project in M48. The activities within the scope of T.5.4.2 and T.5.4.3 are documented by means of two interim reports (D5.6 and D5.7) and a final report (D5.8). The aim is to make the greatest possible contribution to standardisation based on the BIO-SUSHY results.

2. INTRODUCTION & METHODOLOGY

2.1. Information about standardisation process and standards

2.1.1 General

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system or service, or describe in detail a particular method, procedure or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of sharing knowledge and building consensus among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including businesses, consumers and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organized in Technical Committees (TCs), which are subdivided in Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the Standardisation Organisations (National, European and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standards are developed by teams of experts with particular knowledge of the specific or topic being addressed. The members of Technical Committees, sub-committees, and working groups are nominated by the national standardisation bodies (NSB).

2.1.2 International Standardisation Organisations

International Standardisation Organisations develop worldwide applicable, market-driven standards, in a multi-stakeholder environment which ensures that a wide range of technical views are represented, including those relating to social and economic interests.

While not subjected to a specific jurisdiction, International standards facilitate international trade. This contribution has been recognized by the World Trade Organisation (WTO) and the organisations cited below follow the Code of Good Practice for the Preparation, Adoption and Application of Standards of the WTO Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade.

The three International Standardisation Organisations are:

- ISO – International Organisation for Standardisation

ISO is an independent, non-governmental international organisation with a membership of 168 national standards bodies. ISO develops standards in all technical and non-technical fields, but not related to electrotechnology or telecommunications.

- IEC – International Electrotechnical Commission

IEC is a not-for-profit, non-governmental organisation with a membership of 86 national standards bodies. IEC develops standards in fields related to electrotechnology.

- ITU – International Telecommunication Union

ITU is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication technologies. It is based on public-private partnership and currently has a membership of 193 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions.

2.1.3 European Standardisation Organisations

The European Standardisation system plays a major role in the EU Single Market, enabling the free circulation of goods among the countries. The European standardisation system relies on a single standard model. European standards are identically adopted by all their National Members and any conflicting national standard is withdrawn.

European standards facilitate compliance with EU harmonization legislation, hence the entry and free circulation of goods in the EU Single Market, based on a set of requirements equally applicable in all Member States of the European Union.

European Standardisation Organisations work closely with their international level counterparts, to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards. As a result, 31% of CEN standards are identical to ISO standards and 72% of CENELEC standards are identical to IEC standards.

CEN, CENELEC and ETSI have been officially recognized by the European Union and the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) as responsible for developing standards at the European level.

CEN – European Committee for Standardisation

CEN is a non-profit association whose members are the national standards bodies of 34 European countries. It develops standards in fields not related to electrotechnology nor telecommunications. It is the counterpart at the European level of ISO.

- CENELEC – European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation

CENELEC is a non-profit association whose members are the national standards bodies of 34 European countries. It develops standards in fields related to electrotechnology. It is the counterpart at the European level of IEC.

- ETSI – European Telecommunications Standards Institute

ETSI is a non-profit organisation with more than 850 member organisations worldwide. It develops standards for Information and Communications Technologies (ICT).

2.1.4 National Standardisation Organisations

The national standardisation organisations are the organisations officially recognized at the national level as being able to represent all standardisation interests in their country; examples are DIN (Germany), UNE (Spain), AFNOR (France), UNI (Italy) or BSI (Great Britain). They are responsible for developing national standards in their countries and they are members of ISO, IEC, CEN and CENELEC (note that ITU and ETSI have different membership policies). National stakeholders interested in standardisation activities can take part in the process at the European or International level through their national standardisation organisation.

The legal status of national standardisation organisations varies from one country to another. The most typical status is a private non-profit organisation whose members are national business associations and companies, but sometimes the national standardisation organisation is a part of the public administration.

At the European level, the European Standardisation System guarantees that European Standards are identically adopted by all the national standardisation organisations and any conflicting national standard is withdrawn. This means the national catalogues of standards have a significant level of coherence across Europe.

2.1.5 Standardisation documents

Standardisation organisations develop different types of documents, with different levels of consensus and drafting timeframes.

The most widespread document is the “Standard”, a normative document developed and approved by the members of the organisation according to strict consensus procedures. Other types of documents are Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR) and Workshop Agreements (WA), which have lower levels of consensus and a faster drafting timeframe. The latter kinds of documents

can be further processed to become an International Standard if the market has reached a suitable level of consensus.

It is worth mentioning that many European Standards are also adopted as identical national standards by CEN-CENELEC Affiliates, which are the National Standards Bodies of 17 neighbouring countries. Table 1 shows the different kinds of documents developed by international, European and national standardisation organisations and their main characteristics.

Table 1: Characteristics of different standardisation documents

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO IEC	EN	UNE, NF, BS, DIN, UNI, etc. When adopted: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE-ISO, NF-ISO etc.	Elaboration: between 18 and 36 months 2 (CEN/CENELEC) or 3 (ISO/IEC) steps of member approval European: compulsory national adoption Review: every 5 years Revision: whenever needed and as result from a systematic review
Technical Specification	ISO/TS IEC/TS	CEN/TS CLC/TS	When adopted: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	Elaboration: 21 months 1 step of member approval or internal approval in TC European: optional national adoption Review: after 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report	ISO/TR IEC/TR	CEN/TR CLC/TR	When adopted: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	Elaboration: free timeframe Internal approval in TC European: optional national adoption No review required

<p>Workshop Agreement</p>	<p>IWA</p>	<p>CWA</p>	<p>Variable</p>	<p>Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) Internal approval in the Workshop European: optional national adoption Review: after 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)</p>
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There is also an agreement established between European and International Organisations in order to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allows to adopt or develop in parallel each other’s standards with the same content and code.

National standards could also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards. Figure 1 shows possible tracks of standards adoption.

Figure 1: Possible tracks of standards adoption

Additionally, taking into account the nature of information covered by a standard, four types of standards are defined:

- **Fundamental standards** - which concern terminology, conventions, signs and symbols, etc.
- **Test methods and analysis standards** - which determine characteristics of products, materials, etc., for example chemical composition or resistance against environmental influences.
- **Specification standards** - which define characteristics of a product (product standards), or a service (service activities standards) and their performance thresholds such as fitness for use, interface and interoperability, health and safety, environmental protection, etc.

- **Organisation standards** - which describe the functions and relationships of a company, as well as elements such as quality management and assurance, maintenance, value analysis, logistics, project or system management, production management, etc.

The analysis made to present the relevant standards and standards under development in this deliverable includes these four types of standards but with a special focus on test methods and analysis standards and specification standards for the products covered by the BIO-SUSHY project.

2.2. Methodology of identification of relevant standardisation areas

The standardisation landscape was studied considering the main key concepts of BIO-SUSHY, which were previously compiled with and shared with all the partners (see Table 2).

Table 2: List of key concepts acting as a starting point for the identification of standardisation areas and their respective working packages

Key concepts		Work Package					
		WP 1	WP 2	WP 3	WP 4	WP 5	WP 6
1	Nanosafety issues	X					
2	Coatings		X				
3	Oleophobicity		X				
4	Hydrophobicity		X				
5	Coating powder		X				
6	Raw materials: Resins, Thermoplastics, Bio-based products, Additives		X		X		
7	Coating process methodology or technology: Electrostatic spray coating, Powder deposition, Sol-gel		X				
8	Coating characterization: Wettability, oil repellency, adhesion properties		X		X		
9	Case studies: Textiles, Food Packaging, Glass containers, Cosmetics		X				
10	Computational tools: Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Big Data, Data mining, curation and FAIRification			X	X		

11	Safety and toxicity evaluation: Volatile organic compounds (VOCs), Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAs)		X		X		
12	Sustainability and environmental footprint				X		
13	Life cycle				X		
14	Social acceptance	X			X		
15	Business case and market analysis					X	

Considering these key concepts, the following approach was used to identify the main applicable standards:

1. Identification of the relevant Technical Committees within International Standardisation Organisations.

Standardisation work is developed by groups of experts, within technical committees (TCs). TCs are made up of representatives of the industry, public administrations, NGOs, laboratories and other test facilities as well as end users and further stakeholders. Each TC has a well-defined field of activity and its scope. The first step has been the identification of those TCs with a scope related to the tasks and objectives of the BIO-SUSHY Coat project.

The identified technical committees will be the addressees of the dissemination activities and contributions to the ongoing and future standardisation developments based on the results of this project.

2. Identification of the relevant international standards within relevant international TCs.

Although the scope of a TC can be relevant for this project, not the whole standards catalogue of the TC will be relevant. Technical committees usually consist of subcommittees and/or working groups dedicated to the development of standards within the scope of the technical committee but related to specific topics. The second step has been the identification of the relevant standards and standard documents, i.e., technical specifications and technical reports, within each identified TC. This identification is again based on the objectives and tasks of BIO-SUSHY. Keywords and the technologies applied have been used as indicators.

3. Identification of the relevant Technical Committees within European Standardisation Organisations.

Once the relevant international TCs have been identified, the next step is the identification of further European committees. It is possible that there are European committees with (almost) identical scope as international TCs. Usually, these identical committees develop standards and standard documents together (in parallel). But there are also European TCs that have no international equivalent but that are related to the tasks and objectives of the BIO-SUSHY project. As above, future dissemination

activities and the coordination for a contribution to standardisation will be addressed at these committees.

4. Identification of the relevant European standards within relevant European TCs

Once the relevant international standards have been identified, it is necessary to identify the corresponding European standard, if any. If there is a correspondent European standard, it should be used instead of the international version because European standards can contain specific clauses which are necessary to adapt the international standard to the European Regulation, for example. Relevant standards of European TCs without an international equivalent need to be identified as well, so it is necessary to search into the standard catalogue of the European relevant TC looking for these specific European standards.

5. Clustering of thematically related Technical Committees

For a better overview of this report, the various technical committees were assigned to clusters by technical areas or subjects related to the key topics previously compiled.

3. STANDARDISATION RELATED TO BIO-SUSHY

3.1. Technical committees overview

The following list shown in Table 3 presents the European (CEN, CENELEC) and International (ISO, IEC) committees identified as technical bodies working on subjects related to BIO-SUSHY.

Table 3: European and international committees related to BIO-SUSHY

Subject	Technical committee
Coatings	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes
	ISO/TC 35/SC 15 – Protective coatings: concrete surface preparation and coating application
	ISO/TC 35/SC 9/WG 16 – Coating powders
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes
Raw materials	ISO/TC 61 – Plastics
	ISO/TC 61/ SC 5 – Physical- Chemical properties
	ISO/TC 61/ SC 9 – Thermoplastic materials
	CEN/ TC 411 – Bio-based products
Coating characterization	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes
	ISO/TC 6 – Paper, board and pulps
	CEN/TC 172 – Pulp, paper and board
Case studies	ISO/TC 38 – Textiles
	CEN/TC 248 – Textiles and textile products
	CEN/TC 194 – Utensil in contact with food
	ISO/TC 217 – Cosmetics
	CEN/TC 329 – Cosmetics
Nanosafety issues	ISO/TC 229 – Nanotechnologies
	CEN/TC 352 – Nanotechnologies
Toxicity evaluation	ISO/TC 146 – Air quality
	CEN/TC 264 – Air quality
	ISO/TC 61 – Plastics

	CEN/TC 249 – Plastics
	ISO/TC 219 – Floor coverings
	CEN/TC 134 – Resilient and textile floor coverings
	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes
	ISO/TC 147 – Water quality
	CEN/TC 248 – Textile and textile products
Computational tools	ISO/IEC JTC 1 – Information technology
	ISO/TC 46 – Information and documentation
	ISO/TC 171 – Document management application
	ISO/TC 184 – Automation systems and integration
	CEN/CLC JTC 21 – Artificial intelligence
Life cycle	ISO/TC 207 – Environmental management

The following sub-clauses present the European and international Technical Committees, the scope of their activities, the committee structure, the published standards, and their current work programme related to BIO-SUSHY.

The structures of these TCs/SCs are presented in the actual breakdown as an overview, although some of the SCs or WGs base their scope in some knowledge areas, at first, not relevant for BIO-SUSHY.

3.2. Coatings

3.2.1 ISO/TC 35 “Paints and varnishes”

3.2.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of paints, varnishes and related products, including raw materials.

The structure of ISO/TC 35 is:

- SC 9 “General test methods for paints and varnishes”
- SC 12 “Preparation of steel substrates before application of paints and related products”
- SC 14 “Protective paint systems for steel structures”
- SC 15 “Protective coatings: concrete surface preparation and coating application”
- SC 16 “Chemical analysis”
- WG 4 “Binders for paints and varnishes”

- WG 5 “Naval stores”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.2.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 35 has published 294 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 34 documents under development.

ISO/TC 35 standards have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 139 “Paints and varnishes”.

Table 4: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 35

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 1513:2010	EN ISO 1513:2010	Paints and varnishes — Examination and preparation of test samples
ISO 1514:2016	EN ISO 1514:2016	Paints and varnishes — Standard panels for testing
ISO 1518-1:2023	EN ISO 1518-1:2023	Paints and varnishes — Determination of scratch resistance — Part 1: Constant-loading method
ISO 2409:2020	EN ISO 2409:2020	Paints and varnishes — Cross-cut test
ISO 2812-1:2017	EN ISO 2812-1:2017	Paints and varnishes — Determination of resistance to liquids — Part 1: Immersion in liquids other than water
ISO 2812-2:2018	EN ISO 2812-2:2018	Paints and varnishes — Determination of resistance to liquids — Part 2: Water immersion method
ISO 2884-1:1999	EN ISO 2884-1:1999	Paints and varnishes — Determination of viscosity using rotary viscometers — Part 1: Cone-and-plate viscometer operated at a high rate of shear
ISO 3251:2019	EN ISO 3251:2019	Paints, varnishes and plastics — Determination of non-volatile-matter content
ISO 4628-1:2016	EN ISO 4628-1:2016	Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of degradation of coatings — Designation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 1: General introduction and designation system
ISO 4628-2:2016	EN ISO 4628-2:2016	Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of degradation of coatings — Designation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 2: Assessment of degree of blistering

ISO 4628-4:2016	EN ISO 4628-4:2016	Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of degradation of coatings — Designation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 4: Assessment of degree of cracking
ISO 4628-5:2022	EN ISO 4628-5:2022	Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 5: Assessment of degree of flaking
ISO 6270-2:2017	EN ISO 6270-2:2018	Paints and varnishes — Determination of resistance to humidity — Part 2: Condensation (in-cabinet exposure with heated water reservoir)
ISO 11998:2006	EN ISO 11998:2006	Paints and varnishes — Determination of wet-scrub resistance and cleanability of coatings
ISO 15184:2020	EN ISO 15184:2020	Paints and varnishes — Determination of film hardness by pencil test
ISO 8130-1:2019	EN ISO 8130-1:2019	Coating powders — Part 1: Determination of particle size distribution by sieving
ISO 8130-15:2023	x	Coating powders — Part 15: Rheology

3.2.2 CEN/TC 139 “Paints and varnishes”

3.2.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of paints, varnishes and related products. Establishment of methods of test and requirements for coating materials and coatings. Definition of terms.

The structure of CEN/TC 139 is:

- WG 1 “Interior wall and façade coatings”
- WG 2 “Coating systems for wood”
- WG 9 “Testing of coil coated metals”
- WG 10 “Microbiology and leaching of substances”
- WG 13 “Reactive coatings for fire protection”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.2.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/TC 139 has published 341 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 41 documents under development.

Table 5: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 139

Reference	Document title
prEN ISO 8130-15	Coating powders — Part 15: Rheology

3.3. Raw materials

3.3.1 ISO/TC 61 “Plastics”

3.3.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation of nomenclature, methods of test, and specifications applicable to materials and products in the field of plastics, including processing (of products) by assembly in particular, but not limited to, polymeric adhesives, sealing, joining and welding.

Excluded: rubber, lacquers.

Note 1: By agreement, standards in relation to thermoplastic elastomers are developed and maintained by ISO/TC 45 and by ISO/TC 61.

Note 2: Jointing technology (including equipment and training) between plastic pipes (including all types of reinforced plastics), and/or fittings, valves and auxiliary equipment, and the assessment of the properties of the resulting joints are developed and maintained by ISO/TC 138.

The structure of ISO/TC 61 is:

- SC 1 “Terminology”
- SC 2 “Mechanical behaviour”
- SC 4 “Burning behaviour”
- SC 5 “Physical-chemical properties”
- SC 6 “Ageing, chemical and environmental resistance”
- SC 9 “Thermoplastic materials”
- SC 10 “Cellular plastics”
- SC 11 “Products”
- SC 12 “Thermosetting materials”
- SC 13 “Composites and reinforcement fibres”
- SC 14 “Environmental aspects”
- WG 5 “Electrical, Magnetic & Opto-electrical Properties of Plastics and Composites”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.3.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 61 has published 730 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 97 documents under development.

The relevant ISO/TC 61 standard has not been adopted as a European standard.

Table 6: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 61

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 16620-1:2015	x	Plastics — Biobased content — Part 1: General principles

3.3.2. CEN/TC 411 “Bio-based products”

3.3.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

The scope of CEN/TC 411 is:

1. Development of standards for bio-based products covering horizontal aspects. This includes consistent terminology, sampling, certification tools, bio-based content, application of and correlation towards life cycle analysis, sustainability criteria for biomass used and for final products, and aspects where further harmonization is needed on horizontal level;
2. Development of standards for bio-solvents, covering product functionality, biodegradability and, if necessary, product specific aspects not covered under 1.

The structure of CEN/TC 411 is:

- WG 1 “Terminology”
- WG 3 “Bio-based content”
- WG 4 “Sustainability criteria, life cycle analysis and related issues”
- WG 5 “Certification and declaration tools”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.3.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/TC 411 has developed and published 15 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 2 documents under development.

Table 7: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 411

Reference	Document title
CEN/TR 16957:2016	Bio-based products - Guidelines for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the End-of-life phase
EN 16760:2015	Bio-based products - Life Cycle Assessment

CEN/TR 16721:2014	Bio-based products - Overview of methods to determine the bio-based content
CEN/TR 16957:2016	Bio-based products - Guidelines for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the End-of-life phase
EN 16640:2017	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method

3.4. Coating Characterization

3.4.1. ISO/TC 35 “Paints and varnishes”

3.4.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Previously described in section 3.2.1.

3.4.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

Table 8: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 35

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 2409:2020	EN ISO 2409:2020	Paints and varnishes — Cross-cut test
ISO 19403-2:2017	EN ISO 19403-2:2021	Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 2: Determination of the surface free energy of solid surfaces by measuring the contact angle
ISO 19403-5:2017	EN ISO 19403-5:2020	Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 5: Determination of the polar and dispersive fractions of the surface tension of liquids from contact angles measurements on a solid with only a disperse contribution to its surface energy
ISO 19403-7:2017	EN ISO 19403-7:2020	Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 7: Measurement of the contact angle on a tilt stage (roll-off angle)

3.4.2. ISO/TC 6 “Paper, board and pulps”

3.4.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of paper, board pulps cellulosic nanomaterials, and lignins, including terminology, sampling procedures, test methods, product and quality specifications, and the establishment and maintenance of appropriate calibration systems. This includes all types of paper, pulps and board, and products containing any portion of recycled material or material intended for recycling.

The structure of ISO/TC 6 is:

- SC 2 “Test methods and quality specifications for paper and board”
- TG 1 “Cellulosic Nanomaterials”
- TG 2 “Identification of organisations- Environmental issues”
- WG 3 “Optical properties”
- WG 7 “Cores for reels of paper”
- WG 14 “Recycling”
- WG 15 “Pulp methods”
- WG 16 “Lignin analyses”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.4.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 6 published 203 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 18 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 6 have been adopted as European standards, the responsible committee is CEN/TC 172 “Pulp, paper and board”.

Table 9: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 6

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 535:2023	EN ISO 535:2023	Paper and board — Determination of water absorptiveness — Cobb method
ISO 16532-2:2010	x	Paper and board — Determination of grease resistance — Part 2: Surface repellency test
ISO 16532-3:2010	x	Paper and board — Determination of grease resistance — Part 3: Turpentine test for voids in glassine and greaseproof papers

3.5. Case studies

3.5.1. ISO/TC 38 “Textiles”

3.5.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation of:

- fibres, yarns, threads, cords, rope, cloth and other fabricated textile materials; and the methods of test, terminology and definitions relating thereto;
- textile industry raw materials, auxiliaries and chemical products required for processing and testing;
- specifications for textile products.

- microplastics from textile sources and the methods of test, specifications, terminology and definitions relating thereto;
- traceability and responsible sourcing of animal fibers in the textile supply chain and the methods of test, specifications, terminology and definitions relating thereto;
- ethical and environmental issues in the textile supply chain and the methods of test, specifications, terminology and definitions relating thereto.

The structure of ISO/TC 38 is:

- SC 1 "Test for coloured textiles and colorants"
- SC 2 "Cleansing, finishing and water resistance tests"
- SC 20 "Fabric descriptions"
- SC 23 "Fibres and yarns"
- SC 24 "Conditioning atmospheres and physical test for textile fabrics"
- WG 9 "Nonwovens"
- WG 17 "Physiological properties of textiles"
- WG 21 "Ropes, cordage, slings and netting"
- WG 22 "Composition and chemical testing"
- WG 23 "Biological properties of textiles"
- WG 27 "Fabric properties relating to moisture"
- WG 29 "Testing methods for textile products against noxious pests"
- WG 30 "Tests for Biodegradability"
- WG 31 "Natural material for textiles"
- WG 32 "Smart textiles"
- WG 33 "Animal welfare in the textiles supply chain"
- WG 34 "Microplastics for textiles sources"
- WG 35 "Environmental aspects"

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.5.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 38 has published 429 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 33 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 38 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 248 "Textiles and textiles products".

Table 10: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 38

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 4920:2012	EN ISO 4920:2012	Textile fabrics — Determination of resistance to surface wetting (spray test)
ISO 811:2018	EN ISO 811:2018	Textiles — Determination of resistance to water penetration — Hydrostatic pressure test
ISO 3175-1:2017	EN ISO 3175-1:2017	Textiles — Professional care, drycleaning and wet cleaning of fabrics and garments — Part 1: Assessment of performance after cleaning and finishing
ISO 3175-4:2018	EN ISO 3175-4:2018	Textiles — Professional care, drycleaning and wet cleaning of fabrics and garments — Part 4: Procedure for testing performance when cleaning and finishing using simulated wet cleaning
ISO 9865:1991	x	Textiles — Determination of water repellency of fabrics by the Bundesmann rain-shower test
ISO 15496:2018	EN ISO 15496:2018	Textiles — Measurement of water vapour permeability of textiles for the purpose of quality control
ISO 18695:2007	x	Textiles — Determination of resistance to water penetration — Impact penetration test
ISO 22958:2021	x	Textiles — Water resistance — Rain tests: exposure to a horizontal water spray
ISO 23232:2009	x	Textiles — Aqueous liquid repellency — Water/alcohol solution resistance test
ISO 5077/2007	EN ISO 5077/2008	Textiles – Determination of dimensional change in washing and drying
ISO 15797:2017	EN ISO 15797:2017	Textiles – Industrial washing and finishing procedures for testing of workwear
ISO 6330:2021	EN ISO 6330:2021	Textiles – Domestic washing and drying procedures for textile testing

Table 11: Relevant ISO/TC 38 standards under development

Reference	Document title
ISO/FDIS 5157	Textiles — Environmental aspects — Vocabulary

ISO/AWI 11092	Textiles — Physiological effects — Measurement of thermal and water-vapour resistance under steady-state conditions (sweating guarded-hotplate test)
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3.5.2. CEN/TC 194 “Utensil in contact with food”

3.5.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of kitchen, table and household utensils, used in the preparation, cooking, serving and consumption of food and beverage, domestically and in catering establishments. Standardisation of conditions of storage and transportation of catering containers containing prepared foodstuffs.

The structure of CEN/TC 194 is:

- WG 1 “Cookware”
- WG 4 “Cutlery and related items”
- WG 7 “Methods of test for monomers”
- WG 8 “Overall migration”
- WG 9 “Technological suitability testing methods”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.5.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/TC 194 has published 83 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 6 documents under development.

Table 12: Relevant standard from CEN/TC 194

Reference	Document title
CEN/TS 13130-20:1999	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 20: Determination of epichlorohydrin in plastics

3.5.3. CEN/TC 248 “Textiles and textile products”

3.5.3.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation of the following aspects of textiles, textile products and textile components of products: 1) test methods; 2) terms and definitions; 3) specifications, and if necessary classifications, in terms of their expected behaviour, in particular where required by other CEN Technical Committees or the CEC or EFTA. Equipment relevant for the testing and use of textiles.

The structure of CEN/TC 248:

- WG 4 “Coated fabrics”
- WG 9 “Prioritization of research topics”
- WG 10 “Size systems of clothing”
- WG 14 “UV protective properties”
- WG 17 “Hygienic quality of textiles processed in industrial laundries and used in sectors in which it is necessary to control biocontamination”
- WG 20 “Safety of children ´s clothing”
- WG 24 “Test methods for the flammability of textiles”
- WG 25 “Cosmeto-textiles”
- WG 26 “Textiles -Test methods for analysis of EC restricted substances”
- WG 28 “Thermoregulatory properties of textiles and textile products”
- WG 30 “Composition - Qualitative and quantitative analysis of fibres and fibre mixtures”
- WG 31 “Smart textiles and electronic textiles”
- WG 34 “Joint Working Group between CEN/TC 248 and CEN/TC 252 - Risks in the sleeping environment”
- WG 35 “Slide (zip) fasteners”
- WG 37 “Microplastics from textile sources”
- WG 38 “Community face coverings - Guide to minimum requirements, methods of testing and use”
- WG 39 “Circular Economy for textile products and the textile chain”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.5.3.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/TC 248 has published 386 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 36 documents under development.

Table 13: Relevant standards from CEN/TC 248

Reference	Document title
CEN/TS 16822:2015	Textiles and textile products - Self-declared environmental claims - Use of the terms
EN 12280-1:1997	Rubber- or plastics- coated fabrics - Accelerated ageing tests - Part 1: Heat ageing
EN 12280-2:2002	Rubber- or plastic-coated fabrics - Accelerated ageing tests - Part 2: Physical ageing: effect of light or weathering

EN 12280-3:2002	Rubber- or plastic-coated fabrics - Accelerated ageing tests - Part 3: Environmental ageing
EN 1734:1996	Rubber- or plastics coated fabrics - Determination of resistance to water penetration - Low pressure method
EN 29865:1993	Textiles - Determination of water repellency of fabrics by the Bundesmann rain-shower test

Table 14: Relevant CEN/TC 248 standards under development

Reference	Document title
prEN ISO 11092 rev	Textiles — Physiological effects — Measurement of thermal and water-vapour resistance under steady-state conditions (sweating guarded-hotplate test)
prEN ISO 14419 rev	Textiles - Oil repellency - Hydrocarbon resistance test

3.5.4. ISO/TC 217 “Cosmetics”

3.5.4.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of cosmetic products.

The structure of ISO/TC 217 is:

- ISO/TC 217/WG 1 “Microbiological standards and limits”
- ISO/TC 217/WG 3 “Analytical methods”
- ISO/TC 217/WG 4 “Terminology”
- ISO/TC 217/WG 7 “Sun protection test methods”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.5.4.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 217 has published 48 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 3 documents under development.

Table 15: Relevant standard from ISO/TC 217

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 22715:2006	x	Cosmetics - Packaging and labelling

3.6. Nanosafety Issues

3.6.1. ISO/TC 229 “Nanotechnologies”

3.6.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of nanotechnologies that includes either or both of the following:

1. Understanding and control of matter and processes at the nanoscale, typically, but not exclusively, below 100 nanometres in one or more dimensions where the onset of size-dependent phenomena usually enables novel applications,
2. Utilizing the properties of nanoscale materials that differ from the properties of individual atoms, molecules, and bulk matter, to create improved materials, devices, and systems that exploit these new properties.

Specific tasks include developing standards for: terminology and nomenclature; metrology and instrumentation, including specifications for reference materials; test methodologies; modelling and simulations; and science-based health, safety, and environmental practices.

The structure of ISO/TC 229 is:

- JWG 1 “Terminology and nomenclature”
- JWG 2 “Measurement and characterization”
- TG 2 “Sustainability, consumer and societal dimensions of nanotechnologies”
- WG 3 “Health, Safety and Environmental Aspects of Nanotechnologies”
- WG 4 “Material specifications”
- WG 5 “Products and Applications”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.6.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 229 has published 103 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 31 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 229 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 352 “Nanotechnologies”.

Table 16: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 229

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO/TS 4988:2022	x	Nanotechnologies — Toxicity assessment and bioassimilation of manufactured nano-objects in suspension using the unicellular organism <i>Tetrahymena</i> sp.

ISO 10808:2010	EN ISO 10808:2010	Nanotechnologies — Characterization of nanoparticles in inhalation exposure chambers for inhalation toxicity testing
ISO/TR 11360:2010	x	Nanotechnologies — Methodology for the classification and categorization of nanomaterials
ISO/TS 12025:2021	CEN ISO/TS 12025:2021	Nanomaterials — Quantification of nano-object release from powders by generation of aerosols
ISO/TS 12805:2011	x	Nanotechnologies — Materials specifications — Guidance on specifying nano-objects
ISO/TR 12885:2018	x	Nanotechnologies — Health and safety practices in occupational settings
ISO/TS 12901-1:2012	x	Nanotechnologies — Occupational risk management applied to engineered nanomaterials — Part 1: Principles and approaches
ISO/TS 12901-2:2014	x	Nanotechnologies — Occupational risk management applied to engineered nanomaterials — Part 2: Use of the control banding approach
ISO/TR 13014:2012	x	Nanotechnologies — Guidance on physico-chemical characterization of engineered nanoscale materials for toxicologic assessment
ISO/TR 13014:2012/Cor 1:2012	x	Nanotechnologies — Guidance on physico-chemical characterization of engineered nanoscale materials for toxicologic assessment — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO/TR 13121:2011	x	Nanotechnologies — Nanomaterial risk evaluation
ISO/TR 13329:2012	x	Nanomaterials — Preparation of material safety data sheet (MSDS)
ISO/TS 14101:2012	x	Surface characterization of gold nanoparticles for nanomaterial specific toxicity screening: FT-IR method
ISO/TR 14786:2014	x	Nanotechnologies — Considerations for the development of chemical nomenclature for selected nano-objects
ISO/TS 16195:2018	x	Nanotechnologies — Specification for developing representative test materials consisting of nano-objects in dry powder form
ISO/TR 16197:2014	x	Nanotechnologies — Compilation and description of toxicological screening methods for manufactured nanomaterials

ISO/TR 17302:2015	x	Nanotechnologies — Framework for identifying vocabulary development for nanotechnology applications in human healthcare
ISO/TR 18637:2016	x	Nanotechnologies — Overview of available frameworks for the development of occupational exposure limits and bands for nano-objects and their aggregates and agglomerates (NOAAs)
ISO 19007:2018	x	Nanotechnologies — In vitro MTS assay for measuring the cytotoxic effect of nanoparticles
ISO/TR 19057:2017	x	Nanotechnologies — Use and application of acellular in vitro tests and methodologies to assess nanomaterial biodegradability
ISO/TS 19337:2016	x	Nanotechnologies — Characteristics of working suspensions of nano-objects for in vitro assays to evaluate inherent nano-object toxicity
ISO/TS 20660:2019	x	Nanotechnologies — Antibacterial silver nanoparticles — Specification of characteristics and measurement methods
ISO/TS 21633:2021	x	Label-free impedance technology to assess the toxicity of nanomaterials in vitro
ISO/TS 21975:2020	x	Nanotechnologies — Polymeric nanocomposite films for food packaging with barrier properties — Specification of characteristics and measurement methods
ISO/TR 22019:2019	x	Nanotechnologies — Considerations for performing toxicokinetic studies with nanomaterials
ISO/TS 22082:2020	x	Nanotechnologies — Assessment of nanomaterial toxicity using dechorionated zebrafish embryo
ISO/TR 22455:2021	x	Nanotechnologies — High throughput screening method for nanoparticles toxicity using 3D model cells
ISO/TS 23650:2021	x	Nanotechnologies — Evaluation of the antimicrobial performance of textiles containing manufactured nanomaterials
ISO/TS 80004-5:2011	x	Nanotechnologies — Vocabulary — Part 5: Nano/bio interface

Table 17: Relevant ISO/TC 229 standards under development

Reference	Document title
ISO/DTS 10689	Nanotechnologies — Superhydrophobic surfaces and coatings: characteristics and performance assessment
ISO/CD 4962	Nanotechnologies — In vitro nanoparticle acute phototoxicity assay
ISO/AWI TS 5341	Nanotechnologies — Nomenclature — Part 1: General nomenclature
ISO/PRF TS 10818	Nanotechnologies — Textiles containing nanomaterials and nanostructures — Superhydrophobic characteristics and durability assessment
ISO/CD TS 12901-1	Nanotechnologies — Occupational risk management applied to engineered nanomaterials — Part 1: Principles and approaches
ISO/WD TS 12901-2	Nanotechnologies — Occupational risk management applied to engineered nanomaterials — Part 2: Use of the control banding approach
ISO/CD TS 13329	Nanomaterials - Preparation of safety data sheets (SDS)
ISO 19337	Nanotechnologies — Characteristics of working suspensions of nano-objects for in vitro assays to evaluate inherent nano-object toxicity
ISO/FDIS 80004-1	Nanotechnologies - Vocabulary — Part 1: Core vocabulary

3.6.2. CEN/TC 352 “Nanotechnologies”

3.6.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of nanotechnologies that includes either or both of the following:

1. understanding and control of matter and processes at the nanoscale, typically, but not exclusively below 100 nanometres in one or more dimensions, where the onset of size dependent phenomena usually enables novel applications; 2. utilizing the properties of nanoscale materials that differ from the properties of individual atoms, molecules or bulk matter, to create improved materials, devices and systems that exploit these new properties. Specific tasks include developing standards for: classification, terminology and nomenclature; metrology and instrumentation, including specifications for reference materials; test methodologies; modelling and simulation; science-based health, safety and environmental practices; and nanotechnology products and processes. Standards in each of these areas could be specific to a product, process or industry.

The structure of CEN/TC 352 is:

- WG 1 “Measurements, characterization and performance evaluation”
- WG 3 “Health, safety and environmental aspects”

- WG 4 “Manufactured nano-objects in food additives”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.6.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/TC 352 has published 32 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 9 documents under development.

Table 18: Relevant standard from ISO/TC 352

Reference	Document title
CEN/TS 17275:2018	Nanotechnologies - Guidelines for the management and disposal of waste from the manufacturing and processing of manufactured nano-objects

3.7. Toxicity Evaluation

3.7.1. ISO/TC 146 “Air quality”

3.7.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation of tools for air quality characterisation of emissions, workspace air, ambient air, indoor air, in particular measurement methods for air pollutants (particles, gases, odours, micro-organisms) and for meteorological parameters, measurement planning, procedures for Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) and methods for the evaluation of results including the determination of uncertainty.

Excluded:

- the establishment of limit values for air pollutants;
- the air quality in clean rooms;
- radioactive substances.

The structure of ISO/TC 146 is:

- SC 1 “Stationary source emissions”
- SC 2 “Workplace atmospheres”
- SC 3 “Ambient atmospheres”
- SC 4 “General aspects”
- SC 5 “Meteorology”
- SC 6 “Indoor air”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.7.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 146 has published 199 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 28 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 146 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 264 "Air quality".

Table 19: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 146

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 16200-1:2001	x	Workplace air quality — Sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by solvent desorption/gas chromatography — Part 1: Pumped sampling method
ISO 16200-2:2000	x	Workplace air quality — Sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by solvent desorption/gas chromatography — Part 2: Diffusive sampling method
ISO 16000-5:2007	EN ISO 16000-5:2007	Indoor air — Part 5: Sampling strategy for volatile organic compounds (VOCs)
ISO 16000-6:2021	x	Indoor air — Part 6: Determination of organic compounds (VOC, SVOC) in indoor and test chamber air by active sampling on sorbent tubes, thermal desorption and gas chromatography using MS
ISO 16000-9:2006	EN ISO 16000-9:2006	Indoor air — Part 9: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing — Emission test chamber method
ISO 16000-10:2006	EN ISO 16000-10:2006	Indoor air — Part 10: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing — Emission test cell method
ISO 16000-11:2006	EN ISO 16000-11:2006	Indoor air — Part 11: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing — Sampling, storage of samples and preparation of test specimens
ISO 16000-25:2011	x	Indoor air — Part 25: Determination of the emission of semi-volatile organic compounds by building products — Micro-chamber method
ISO 16017-1:2000	EN ISO 16017-1:2000	Indoor, ambient and workplace air — Sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by sorbent tube/thermal desorption/capillary gas chromatography — Part 1: Pumped sampling

ISO 16017-2:2003	EN ISO 16017-2:2003	Indoor, ambient and workplace air — Sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by sorbent tube/thermal desorption/capillary gas chromatography — Part 2: Diffusive sampling
ISO/DIS 16000-9	prEN ISO 16000-9	Indoor air — Part 9: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing - Emission test chamber method
ISO/DIS 16000-11	prEN ISO 16000-11	Indoor air — Part 11: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing — Sampling, storage of samples and preparation of test specimens

3.7.2. ISO/TC 35 “Paints and varnishes”

3.7.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Previously described in section 3.2.1.

3.7.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

Standards of ISO/TC 35 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 139 “Paints and varnishes”.

Table 20: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 35

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO/TR 5601:2023	x	Paints and varnishes — Determination of volatile organic compound (VOC) and/or semi-volatile organic compound (SVOC) content — Best practices for the selection of test methods
ISO 11890-1:2007	EN ISO 11890-1:2007	Paints and varnishes — Determination of volatile organic compound (VOC) content — Part 1: Difference method
ISO 11890-2:2020	EN ISO 11890-2:2020	Paints and varnishes — Determination of volatile organic compounds (VOC) and/or semi volatile organic compounds (SVOC) content — Part 2: Gas-chromatographic method
ISO 17895:2005	EN ISO 17895:2005	Paints and varnishes — Determination of the volatile organic compound content of low-VOC emulsion paints (in-can VOC)

Table 21: Relevant ISO/TC 35 under development

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO/AWI 11890-1	EN ISO 11890-1	Paints and varnishes — Determination of volatile organic compound (VOC) content — Part 1: Difference method
ISO 11890-2:2020/CD Amd 1	EN ISO 11890-2:2020	Paints and varnishes — Determination of volatile organic compounds (VOC) and/or semi volatile organic compounds (SVOC) content — Part 2: Gas-chromatographic method — Amendment 1
ISO/DIS 17895	x	Paints and varnishes — Determination of volatile organic compound (VOC) — Gas-chromatographic method with headspace injection for VOC determination

3.7.3 ISO/TC 147 “Water quality”

3.7.3.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of water quality, including definition of terms, sampling of waters, measurement and reporting of water characteristics.

Excluded:

- limits of acceptability for water quality.

The structure of ISO/TC 147 is:

- SC 1 “Terminology”
- SC 2 “Physical, chemical and biochemical methods”
- SC 3 “Radioactivity measurements”
- SC 4 “Microbiological methods”
- SC 5 “Biological methods”
- SC 6 “Sampling (general methods)”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.7.3.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 147 has published 332 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 41 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 147 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 230 “Water analysis”.

Table 22: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 147

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 17943:2016	EN ISO 17943:2016	Water quality — Determination of volatile organic compounds in water — Method using headspace solid-phase micro-extraction (HS-SPME) followed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)
ISO 20595:2018	EN ISO 20595:2018	Water quality — Determination of selected highly volatile organic compounds in water — Method using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry by static headspace technique (HS-GC-MS)
ISO 10301:1997	EN ISO 10301:1997	Water quality - Determination of highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons - Gas-chromatographic methods
ISO 21675:2019	x	Water quality — Determination of perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in water — Method using solid phase extraction and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

3.7.4. ISO/TC 61 “Plastics”

3.7.4.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Previously described in 3.3.1.

3.7.4.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 61 has published 730 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 97 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 61 have been adopted as European standards, the responsible committee is CEN/TC 249 “Plastics”.

Table 23: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 61

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 14855-1:2012	EN ISO 14855-1:2012	Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions — Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide — Part 1: General method
ISO 14855-2:2018	EN ISO 14855-2:2018	Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions — Method by analysis of evolved carbon

		dioxide — Part 2: Gravimetric measurement of carbon dioxide evolved in a
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3.7.5. ISO/TC 219 “Floor coverings”

3.7.5.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of textile, resilient and laminate floor coverings.

The structure of ISO/TC 219 is:

- WG 1 “Textile floor coverings”
- WG 2 “Resilient floor coverings”
- WG 3 “Laminate floor coverings”
- WG 4 “Horizontal topics”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.7.5.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 219 has developed and published 83 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 6 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/TC 219 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/TC 134 “Resilient and textile floor coverings”.

Table 24: Relevant standard from ISO/TC 219

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 10580:2010	EN ISO 10580:2012	Resilient, textile and laminate floor coverings — Test method for volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions

3.7.6. CEN/TC 139 “Paints and varnishes”

3.7.6.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Previously described in section 3.2.2.

3.7.6.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

Table 25: Relevant standard from ISO/TC 139

Reference	Document title
EN 16074:2019	Paints and varnishes - Determination of non-volatile-matter content and spreading rate of coil coating materials

3.7.7. CEN/TC 248 “Textile and textile products”

3.7.7.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Previously described in 3.5.3.

3.7.7.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/TC 248 has published 386 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 36 documents under development.

Table 26: Relevant standards from CEN/TC 248

Reference	Document title
EN 17681-1:2022	Textiles and textile products - Organic fluorine - Part 1: Determination of non-volatile compounds by extraction method using liquid chromatography
EN 17681-2:2022	Textiles and textile products - Organic fluorine - Part 2: Determination of volatile compounds by extraction method using gas chromatography

3.8. Computational tools

3.8.1. ISO/IEC JTC 1 “Information technology”

3.8.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of information technology.

The structure of ISO/IEC JTC 1 is:

- SC 2 “Coded character sets”
- SC 6 “Telecommunications and information exchange between systems”
- SC 7 “Software and systems engineering”
- SC 17 “Cards and security devices for personal identification”
- SC 22 “Programming languages, their environments and system software interfaces”
- SC 23 “Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage”
- SC 24 “Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation”
- SC 25 “Interconnection of information technology equipment”
- SC 27 “Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection”
- SC 28 “Office equipment”
- SC 29 “Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information”
- SC 31 “Automatic identification and data capture techniques”
- SC 32 “Data management and interchange”

- SC 34 “Document description and processing languages”
- SC 35 “User interfaces”
- SC 36 “Information technology for learning, education and training”
- SC 37 “Biometrics”
- SC 38 “Cloud computing and distributed platforms”
- SC 39 “Sustainability, IT and data centres”
- SC 40 “IT service management and IT governance”
- SC 41 “Internet of things and digital twins”
- SC 42 “Artificial intelligence”
- SC 43 “Brain-computer interfaces”

The homepage of technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.8.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/IEC JTC 1 has published 3407 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 473 documents under development.

Standards of ISO/IEC JTC 1 have been adopted as European standards; the responsible committee is CEN/JTC 21 “Artificial intelligence”.

Table 27: Relevant standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO/IEC TS 4213:2022	x	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Assessment of machine learning classification performance
ISO/IEC 22989:2022	prEN ISO/IEC 22989	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology
ISO/IEC 23053:2022	prEN ISO/IEC 23053	Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML)
ISO/IEC 23894:2023	x	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance on risk management
ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021	x	Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making
ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020	x	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence

ISO/IEC TR 24030:2021	x	Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Use cases
ISO/IEC TR 24372:2021	x	Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Overview of computational approaches for AI systems

Table 28: Relevant ISO/IEC JTC 1 standards under development

Reference	Document title
ISO/IEC CD 5259-1	Artificial intelligence — Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) — Part 1: Overview, terminology, and examples
ISO/IEC CD 5259-2	Artificial intelligence — Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) — Part 2: Data quality measures
ISO/IEC CD 5259-3	Artificial intelligence — Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) — Part 3: Data quality management requirements and guidelines
ISO/IEC CD 5259-4	Artificial intelligence — Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) — Part 4: Data quality process framework
ISO/IEC CD 5259-5	Artificial intelligence — Data quality for analytics and machine learning (ML) — Part 5: Data quality governance
ISO/IEC DIS 5339	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance for AI applications
ISO/IEC DIS 5392	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Reference architecture of knowledge engineering
ISO/IEC AWI TS 6254	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Objectives and approaches for explainability of ML models and AI systems
ISO/IEC FDIS 8183	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Data life cycle framework
ISO/IEC AWI TS 17847	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Verification and validation analysis of AI systems
ISO/IEC AWI TR 17903	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of machine learning computing devices
ISO/IEC CD TR 24030	Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Use cases

3.8.2. ISO/TC 46 “Information and documentation”

3.8.2.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation of practices relating to libraries, documentation and information centres, publishing, archives, records management, museum documentation, indexing and abstracting services, and information science.

The structure of ISO/TC 46 is:

- SC 4 “Technical interoperability”
- SC 8 “Quality-Statistics and performance evaluation”
- SC 9 “Identification and description”
- SC 10 “Requirements for document storage and conditions for preservation”
- SC 11 “Archives/records management”
- AHG 2 “Terminology Coordination Group”
- WG 2 “Coding of country names and related entities”
- WG 3 “Conversion of written languages”
- WG 4 “Terminology of information and documentation”
- WG 13 “Information Governance”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.8.2.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 46 has published 128 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 18 documents under development.

The relevant ISO/TC 46 standard has not been adopted as a European standard.

Table 29: Relevant standard from ISO/TC 46

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 20614:2017	x	Information and documentation — Data exchange protocol for interoperability and preservation

3.8.3. ISO/TC 171 “Document management applications”

3.8.3.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation of technologies and processes involving capture, indexing, storage, retrieval, distribution and communication, presentation, migration, exchange, preservation, integrity maintenance and disposal in the field of document management applications. Documents may be managed in micrographic or electronic form.

This includes:

- quality control and integrity maintenance;
- input/output quality of documents (micrographic or electronic)

- implementation, inspection and quality control procedures for storage, use and preservation of documents (micrographic or electronic), including supportive metadata;
- applications involving workflow (process management) in an enterprise and on the Internet;
- maintenance of quality and integrity during information exchange between systems;
- procedures and processes supporting legal admissibility and/or integrity and security;
- management of related audit trail information.

The structure of ISO/TC 171 is:

- SC 1 “Quality, preservation and integrity of information”
- SC 2 “Document file formats, EDMS systems and authenticity of information”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.8.3.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 171 has developed and published 106 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 11 documents under development.

The relevant ISO/TC 171 standards has not been adopted as a European standard.

Table 30: Relevant standard from ISO/TC 171

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO/TR 22299:2018	x	Document management — Digital file format recommendations for long-term storage

3.8.4. ISO/TC 184 “Automation systems and integration”

3.8.4.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of automation systems and their integration for design, sourcing, manufacturing, production and delivery, support, maintenance and disposal of products and their associated services. Areas of standardisation include information systems, automation and control systems and integration technologies.

Note: There will be active collaboration with the relevant technical committees responsible for areas such as machines, manufacturing resources and facilities, robotics, electrical and electronic equipment, PLC for general application, quality management, industrial safety, information technologies, multi-media capabilities, and multi-modal communication networks.

The structure of ISO/TC 184 is:

- SC 1 “Industrial cyber and physical device control”
- SC 4 “Industrial data”

- SC 5 “Interoperability, integration and architectures for enterprise systems and automation applications”
- AG 2 “Digital Twin”
- AHG 3 “Liaison review”
- JWG 21 “Joint ISO/TC 184 – IEC/TC 65/JWG 21- Smart Manufacturing Reference Model (s) linked to ISO/TC 184”
- TF 2 “Supermeeting organisation”
- WG 6 “Asset intensive industry interoperability”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.8.4.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 184 has published 888 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 56 documents under development.

The relevant ISO/TC 184 standards has not been adopted as a European standard.

Table 31: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 184

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 11354-1:2011	x	Advanced automation technologies and their applications — Requirements for establishing manufacturing enterprise process interoperability — Part 1: Framework for enterprise interoperability

3.8.5. CEN/CLC JTC 21 “Artificial Intelligence”

3.8.5.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

The JTC shall produce standardisation deliverables in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and related use of data, as well as provide guidance to other technical committees concerned with Artificial Intelligence. The JTC shall also consider the adoption of relevant international standards and standards from other relevant organisations, like ISO/IEC JTC 1 and its subcommittees, such as SC 42 Artificial intelligence. The JTC shall produce standardisation deliverables to address European market and societal needs and to underpin primarily EU legislation, policies, principles, and values.

The structure of CEN/CLC JTC 21 is:

- WG 1 “Strategic Advisory Group”
- WG 2 “Operational aspects”
- WG 3 “Engineering aspects”
- WG 4 “Foundational and societal aspects”

The homepage of the technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.8.5.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), CEN/CLC/ JTC 21 is currently developing 21 documents.

Table 32: Relevant CEN/CLC JTC 21 standards under development

Reference	Document title
prCEN ISO/IEC/TS 12791	Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Treatment of unwanted bias in classification and regression machine learning tasks
prCEN/TR XXX	AI Risks - Check List for AI Risks Management
prCEN/TR XXX	Data Governance and data quality for AI in the European context
prEN ISO/IEC 23053	Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML) (ISO/IEC 23053:2022)

3.9. Life cycle

3.9.1. ISO/TC 207 “Environmental management”

3.9.1.1. Introduction, scope and structure of the technical committee

Standardisation in the field of environmental management to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.

Excluded: test methods of pollutants, setting limit values and levels of environmental performance, and standardisation of products.

The structure of ISO/TC 207 is:

- SC 1 “Environmental management systems”
- SC 2 “Environmental auditing and related environmental investigations”
- SC 3 “Environmental labelling”
- SC 4 “Environmental performance evaluation”
- SC 5 “Life cycle assessment”
- SC 7 “Greenhouse gas and climate change management and related activities”

The homepage of technical committee with further information on, for example, the Business Plan of the TC can be found [here](#).

3.9.1.2. List of relevant standards and standards under development

As of today (May 2023), ISO/TC 207 has published 67 standards, technical specifications and technical reports. There are currently 16 documents under development.

The relevant ISO/TC 207 standards have been adopted as European standard; the responsible committee is CEN/SS S26 “Environmental Management”.

Table 33: Relevant standards from ISO/TC 207

Reference	Adopted by CEN	Document title
ISO 14040:2006	EN ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework
ISO 14044:2006	EN ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines

Table 34: Relevant ISO/TC 207 standards under development

Reference	Document title
ISO/CD 14075	Principles and framework for social life cycle assessment
ISO/WD TS 14076	Eco-Technoeconomic Analyses: Principles, requirements and guidelines

4. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This report brings together the technical standardisation committees of interest for the BIO-SUSHY project at the European and international level on the basis of a detailed analysis. By making this report available, the awareness of all partners in the project is raised that there is an extensive basis of potentially relevant standards. This can also prevent any duplication of work.

This document D5.5 as result of subtask T5.4.1 forms the basis for the activities of subtask T5.4.2 on the contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments, which extends to the end of the project. The developments within the relevant technical committees will be monitored and reported to the project partners. This information will be included in deliverables: “D5.6 First update on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation roadmap” (M12), “D5.7 Second update on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation roadmap” (M24) and “D5.8 Final report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation roadmap” (M48).

Subtask T5.4.2 will now aim to investigate the standardisation potential of the results being generated in BIO-SUSHY, enabling the project to interact with the related technical standardisation committees, assessing to what extent the relationships with the committees should be and using the standardisation system as a rapid and much more focused dissemination tool to market stakeholders.

Based on the above results, BIO-SUSHY will seek if there is an option to contribute to the development of new standards on specific topics, related to the project objectives. In case the inclusion of the project results in new or future standards that can be easily used by European or international industry and research is achieved, it will increase the impact of the project and contribute positively to the transfer of the knowledge generated in the framework of the project to industry and society.

In order to be able to use the standardisation system as a tool for the dissemination and exploitation of project results and interaction with market actors, it will be necessary to decide on the type of interaction with the technical standardisation committees relevant to BIO-SUSHY (see Table 3). UNE will provide the necessary technical support for such interaction.

Specific tasks may be performed in relation to the standardisation works of the identified TCs. Depending on the assessment by BIO-SUSHY partners of the impact of the identified standardisation TCs on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees, several actions can be performed, for example:

- the follow up of the standardisation activity through updates reported by UNE, supported by the technical partners;
- the dissemination of the BIO-SUSHY project progress by delivering reports to the relevant TCs Secretaries or by attending relevant technical committees' meetings;

- the proposal of standardisation activities to relevant TCs, e.g. revision or modification of existing standards, participation in the development of ongoing standards, proposals of new standards, etc. In the case of new standards, the most appropriate option in the framework of a Horizon Europe project is the development of fast-track standards, such as CEN-CENELEC Workshop Agreements (CWA).

Consequently, the following objectives have been achieved with the production of this deliverable:

- Identification of documents (Standards, Technical Specifications and Technical Reports) that can be directly applied in the BIO-SUSHY activities, or/and that can be used as valuable information source.
- Identification of relevant standardisation Technical Committees for BIO-SUSHY project, allowing the monitorization of their future activities.
- Awareness of the present standardisation framework around the BIO-SUSHY knowledge areas, that will allow in the next steps to identify possible contributions of the BIO-SUSHY project to the on-going and future standardisation developments.
- Insight into the state of the art, that will be the base for the specification of a BIO-SUSHY strategy concerning its interaction with the European standardisation system.

